

The Effect of Barriers to Use on Innovation Resistance and It's Effect on Actual Usage of the OneFlux CRM System at PT Dayamitra Telekomunikasi

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ABSTRACT: The purpose of this study is to explore the variables influencing how the OneFlux CRM system is actually used within PT Dayamitra Telekomunikasi Tbk (Mitratel), based on the development of the Innovation Resistance Theory model. OneFlux is an integrated digital system developed to improve operational efficiency and infrastructure data management. However, its adoption rate remains low across several regions, with usage levels below 50%. This research adopts a quantitative methodology utilizing Structural Equation Modeling (SEM), based on responses obtained from 100 individuals who use the OneFlux system. The study examines variables comprising functional barriers—namely Usage Barrier, Value Barrier, and Risk Barrier—as well as psychological barriers such as Tradition Barrier and Image Barrier, and Technology Anxiety, all in relation to Innovation Resistance, as well as the influence of Innovation Resistance on Actual Usage. The findings indicate that Value Barrier, Risk Barrier, Tradition Barrier, and Technology Anxiety significantly and positively impact Innovation Resistance, whereas Usage Barrier and Image Barrier do not exhibit a statistically significant effect. Additionally, Innovation Resistance has a significant negative effect on Actual Usage. This study provides a theoretical contribution by extending the application of IRT within the context of mandatory system usage and by introducing Technology Anxiety as a new variable. From a managerial perspective, the findings offer strategic direction to reduce user resistance by enhancing perceived value, mitigating risk, shifting work habits, and providing training to lower technology-related anxiety.

KEYWORDS: Actual Usage, IRT, Innovation Resistance, Technology anxiety, OneFlux

1. INTRODUCTION

Mitratel, or PT Dayamitra Telekomunikasi Tbk, is a subsidiary of PT Telkom Indonesia (Persero) Tbk, operating in the telecommunications infrastructure sector. The company entered the telecommunication tower business in 2008. OneFlux is a digital platform developed by Mitratel to streamline and unify data management and service operations within the telecommunications infrastructure domain. The system is designed to integrate various business processes into a centralized platform, creating a single source of real-time data. As the business grows and technology advances, challenges in data management, customer service, and operational efficiency have increasingly affected Mitratel as one of the major telecommunication tower providers in Indonesia. With over 39,000 towers and more than 59,000 tenants, Mitratel faces considerable difficulties in managing data related to tower locations, conditions, and utilization. Prior to the implementation of OneFlux, data was fragmented across multiple systems, making it difficult to obtain consistent and real-time information.

Mitratel needed a platform capable of integrating its various business processes to ensure systematic operational functions. Customers also require fast and easy access to data related to Mitratel's products and services. Under the previous systems, customers often faced delays or difficulties in obtaining such information. Innovation and creativity, supported by information and digital literacy, are widely recognized as key elements in solving modern challenges. Therefore, societies, companies, and institutions aiming to solve problems, develop innovative products, or create new processes must rely on individuals who are creative, capable of innovative thinking, and who foster a culture of creativity and innovation within their environments (Šorgo et al., 2021: 553) [1]. Despite the introduction of OneFlux, most regional offices within Mitratel have not yet fully utilized the application, as shown by its usage rate remaining below 50% across all regions. This indicates the need to evaluate how OneFlux is being used. It is important to examine the factors influencing users' willingness to adopt the OneFlux application, as the success of its implementation heavily depends on user participation. To better understand consumer behavior related to resistance, this

study applies the Innovation Resistance Theory (IRT) mode (Kaur et al., 2020: 2) [2]. Innovation Resistance Theory (IRT) is a relatively new theoretical concept compared to traditional adoption models. Ram (1987) was the first to argue that resistance is not merely the opposite of adoption. Other researchers support this view, stating that resistance to innovation is not necessarily a separate attitude, but can coexist with adoption (e.g. Oh, Park, & Min, 2019 in Talwar et al., 2021: 4) [3]. Ram dan Sheth (1989) in Talwar et al., (2021: 4) [3] proposed that Innovation Resistance Theory (IRT) provides a theoretical framework to understand the factors that cause consumers to reject innovation. The theory suggests that consumers are more likely to reject innovations that conflict with their beliefs or personal values. Research by Kaur et al., (2020) [2] applying IRT in the context of mobile payments found that usage, risk, and value barriers were negatively related to the intention to use mobile payments. Meanwhile, only usage and value barriers were negatively associated with users' willingness to recommend the service. Mitratel hopes to foster sustained usage behavior regarding the OneFlux technology. Based on the explanation above, this study aims to explore the factors influencing the adoption of OneFlux CRM technology using the Innovation Resistance Theory (IRT) model. The research expands the model by including the variables Technology Anxiety and Innovation Resistance as factors that may influence Actual Usage.

1.1 Objectives

The objectives of this research were derived from the background and problem formulation, and can be summarized as follows :

1. To analyze respondents' perceptions of all variables studied in relation to the OneFlux CRM technology
2. To examine the influence of Usage Barriers, Value Barriers, Risk Barriers, Tradition Barriers, Image Barriers, and Technology Anxiety on Innovation Resistance toward the OneFlux CRM technology.
3. To investigate the impact of Innovation Resistance on users' actual usage with the OneFlux CRM platform

2. LITERATURE REVIEW AND HIPOTHESIS

2.1 Strategic Management

Strategic management refers to the combination of both art and science in crafting, executing, and assessing cross-functional decisions that help an organization realize its goals. It emphasizes the integration of key business functions, including management, marketing, finance, accounting, operations, and information systems, to ensure overall organizational success. Moreover, it is often viewed as an executive-level function that involves distributing resources strategically across various products and geographic areas to establish a sustainable competitive advantage (Fred R. David et al., 2023) [4]. According to Fred R. David et al., (2023) [4] the strategic management process consists of three main stages:

1. Strategy Formulation

This phase involves defining the organization's vision and mission, identifying both external opportunities and threats, assessing internal strengths and weaknesses, setting long-term goals, developing strategic alternatives, and selecting the most effective course of action..

2. Strategy Implementation

In this phase, the organization focuses on setting annual objectives, designing policies, motivating staff, and allocating resources to ensure that the chosen strategies are executed effectively.

3. Strategy Evaluation

The final phase is dedicated to monitoring and evaluating the outcomes of the implemented strategies to determine whether they are producing the expected results.

2.2 Digital Transformation

Digital transformation is a significant organizational shift driven by the use of information technology, computing, communication tools, and internet networks to improve performance and work processes (Vial, 2019) [18]. This process leads organizations to become more data-driven and encourages the adoption of technologies such as business intelligence (BI). Digital transformation is widely recognized as a catalyst for change across various sectors, especially in the business world, influencing nearly every aspect of human life through the use of technology and digitalization (Tulungen et al., 2022: 1117) [5]. According to a study by (Dodie Tricahyono, Mochamad Ryan Ferdiansyah,2023) [18] in the hospitality industry, hotels that have implemented digital transformation are more likely to gain a competitive advantage compared to those that have not fully embraced the transformation.

2.3 Innovation Resistance Theory (IRT)

Innovation Resistance Theory serves as a conceptual framework aimed at explaining consumer tendencies to reject or resist the adoption of new innovations (Kaur et al., 2020) [2]. Consumers often encounter various barriers that prevent them from accepting innovation. These forms of resistance are generally segmented into two major classifications—functional and psychological impediments. Functional barriers typically arise when consumers perceive that adopting an innovation will bring significant changes to their routines. These barriers include three main aspects: usage barriers, value barriers, and risk barriers. On the other hand, psychological barriers stem from conflicts between the innovation and the consumer's personal beliefs or mindset. These consist of two key factors: tradition barriers and image barriers. Successful implementation of innovation—particularly digital innovation—within a company can significantly enhance operational efficiency, increase sales, and improve market competitiveness (Mohammad Riza Sutjipto, Almu Zahwa, Dwi Fitriзал Salim, 2025)[20]

2.4 Technology Anxiety

Technology anxiety describes the sense of unease or apprehension individuals may feel when they are faced with using or thinking about technology in real-life contexts (Chen et al., 2024:5) [6]. As information technology continues to advance rapidly, this form of anxiety has become increasingly widespread, coinciding with the normalization of digital tools and applications in daily activities (Widodo dan Pratama, 2020:2340) [7]. According to Yang and Forney, as cited in Widodo dan Salmandani (2023:907) [8] It is defined as a person's mental response regarding their confidence and openness toward using technology-oriented applications or devices.

2.5 Actual Usage

Actual usage (AU) refers to the extent to which a system or technology is genuinely used by individuals in their real-life activities. This variable is different from intention to use, as it reflects actual behavior rather than just a user's intention or attitude toward using the system. According to Venkatesh et al. (2012) [9] in the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT), actual usage is the logical outcome of an already-formed intention to use and serves as a key indicator of the successful adoption of an information technology system.

2.6 Hypothesis

The hypotheses formulated in this study aim to verify the presumed relationships between variables, with the goal of providing insights for addressing the identified problems. Based on the research framework, the following hypotheses are proposed:

- H1: Usage barriers (UB) positively effect the innovation resistance (IR) in the use of OneFlux technology
- H2 : Value barriers (VB) positively effect the innovation resistance (IR) in the use of OneFlux technology
- H3 : Risk barriers (RB) positively effect the innovation resistance (IR) in the use of OneFlux technology
- H4 : Traditional barriers (TB) positively effect the innovation resistance (IR) in the use of OneFlux technology
- H5 : Image barriers (IB) positively effect the innovation resistance (IR) in the use of OneFlux technology
- H6 : Technology anxiety (TA) positively effect the innovation resistance (IR) in the use of OneFlux technology
- H7 : Innovation Resistance (IR) negatively effect the actual usage (AU) of OneFlux technology

3. RESEARCH METHOD

This research is classified as explanatory in nature, as it focuses on investigating and interpreting the connections between two or more variables. The research follows a positivist paradigm, grounded in the philosophy of positivism. The positivist approach views the world through a scientific lens (Prayogi, 2021:78) [10]. On this context, the study was conducted by collecting empirical data through surveys or observations of OneFlux technology users. This research employs a cross-sectional design, where data is collected only once within a specific period, and the unit of analysis is a group (Kurniawati et al., 2024: 270) [11]. A quantitative method is used in this study, which focuses on objectively measuring data, behavior, opinions, or attitudes. This approach is commonly used as it is considered suitable for testing models or hypotheses that have been formulated (Indrawati, 2015) [19]. This study employs several independent variables, including Usage Barriers (UB), Value Barriers (VB), and Risk Barriers (RB), which are classified as functional barriers. Additionally, Tradition Barriers (TB) and Image Barriers (IB) are included as psychological barriers. Another independent variable examined in this research is Technology Anxiety (TA). The dependent variable in this research is Actual Usage.

4. DATA COLLECTION

The number of respondents was determined based on Slovin’s formula for sample size calculation (Sugiono (2021) [12], resulting in total of 100 respondents, all of whom are users of the OneFlux system. A questionnaire was designed to collect data related to Value Barriers (VB), Risk Barriers (RB), Tradition Barriers (TB), Image Barriers (IB), Technology Anxiety (TA), and Actual Usage.

5. RESULTS

In line with the objectives of this study, the following variables were used: Actual Use (Y), Innovation Resistance (IR) (Z), Usage Barrier (UB) (X1), Value Barrier (VB) (X2), Risk Barrier (RB) (X3), Tradition Barrier (TB) (X4), Image Barrier (IB) (X5), and Technology Anxiety (TA) (X6). This study employed SmartPLS (v4.1.0.2) to perform Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) for hypothesis testing and model evaluation.

Gambar _ Model Penelitian Dari Penulis

5.1 Reability Analysis & Convergence Validity

The outer model measurement was conducted by testing the validity and reliability of the indicators that form the latent variables, including Actual Use, Innovation Resistance, Usage Barrier, Value Barrier, Risk Barrier, Tradition Barrier, Image Barrier, and Technology Anxiety. SmartPLS assesses the outer model using four fundamental metrics, namely convergent validity, discriminant validity, composite reliability, and Cronbach’s alpha. According to the factor loading criteria, each indicator must have an outer loading greater than 0.70 or an Average Variance Extracted (AVE) greater than 0.50 (Putri, 2023). The output table shows that all indicators have outer loadings above 0.70, which means they are valid indicators for their respective latent variables. The AVE results also show that all constructs — Actual Use (Y), Innovation Resistance (Z), Usage Barrier (X1), Value Barrier (X2), Risk Barrier (X3), Tradition Barrier (X4), Image Barrier (X5), and Technology Anxiety (X6) — have AVE values above 0.50. This confirms that convergent validity is achieved, as all indicators meet the threshold. A construct is considered to have good reliability if its composite reliability value is greater than 0.70. The results show that all constructs meet this criterion: UB (0.753), VB (0.809), RB (0.852), TB (0.843), IB (1.123), TA (0.866), IR (0.845), and AU (0.882). Similarly, Cronbach’s Alpha values for all constructs are above 0.70, indicating internal consistency: UB (0.741), VB (0.806), RB (0.847), TB (0.839), IB (0.921), TA (0.862), IR (0.844), and AU (0.871). Thus, all constructs in the model demonstrate strong reliability. The R² value for the first equation model is 0.746, meaning that the independent variables (UB, VB, RB, TB, IB, and TA) explain 74.6% of the variance in Innovation Resistance (IR), while the remaining 25.4% is accounted for by variables outside the scope of the model. For the second model, the R² value is 0.397, indicating that the combination of UB, VB, RB, TB, IB, TA, and IR explains 39.7% of the variance in Actual Usage (AU). The other 60.3% is attributed to external factors not captured in the present model.

Reability Analysis & Convergence validity

Construct	Measurement Items	Factor Loading/Coefficient (t-value)	AVE	Compoiste Reability	R Square	Cronbachs Alpha
<i>Actual Use</i>	AU 1	0.901	0.794	0.882	0.397	0.871
	AU 2	0.906				
	AU 3	0.866				
<i>Innovation Resistance (IR)</i>	IR 1	0.812	0.682	0.845	0.746	0.844
	IR 2	0.851				
	IR 3	0.825				
	IR 4	0.815				
<i>Usage Barrier (UB)</i>	UB 1	0.819	0.656	0.753		0.741
	UB 2	0.831				
	UB 3	0.779				
<i>Value Barrier (VB)</i>	VB 1	0.910	0.838	0.809		0.806
	VB 2	0.921				
<i>Risk Barrier (RB)</i>	RB 1	0.893	0.766	0.852		0.847
	RB 2	0.900				
	RB 3	0.831				
<i>Tradition Barrier (TB)</i>	TB 1	0.902	0.756	0.843		0.839
	TB 2	0.860				
	TB 3	0.846				
<i>Image Barrier (IB)</i>	IB 1	0.980	0.922	1.123		0.921
	IB 2	0.940				
<i>Technology Anxiety (TA)</i>	TA 1	0.875	0.785	0.866		0.862
	TA 2	0.923				
	TA 3	0.858				

5.2 Correlation Matrix

The correlation matrix is a table that shows the relationships between variables in a model using correlation values. The values on the diagonal (highlighted in bold) indicate the square root of the AVE for each construct, which indicates discriminant validity. According to the standard criteria for discriminant validity, For each variable, the AVE value on the diagonal must exceed the correlation coefficients it shares with other variables in the corresponding row or column. Based on the table, all diagonal values (AU: 0.891, IB: 0.960, IR: 0.826, RB: 0.875, TA: 0.886, TB: 0.870, UB: 0.810, VB: 0.915) are indeed higher than the respective inter-variable correlations. Therefore, it can be concluded that the model meets the minimum standard for discriminant validity.

Correlation Matrix Tabel

	AU	IB	IR	RB	TA	TB	UB	VB
AU	0.891							
IB	0.128	0.960						
IR	-0.630	-0.130	0.826					
RB	-0.443	-0.158	0.708	0.875				
TA	-0.625	-0.172	0.714	0.541	0.886			

TB	-0.476	-0.204	0.688	0.700	0.607	0.870		
UB	-0.640	-0.112	0.449	0.356	0.496	0.219	0.810	
VB	-0.552	0.005	0.614	0.390	0.449	0.304	0.498	0.915

5.3 Pengukuran Hypothesis

Hypothesis testing refers to a statistical technique for assessing assumptions regarding population parameters using sample data. The procedure begins with the development of a null hypothesis (H_0) indicating no effect or association, alongside an alternative hypothesis (H_1) proposing the existence of an effect or connection. The standard criterion for decision-making is usually based on the p-value (probability of error). A significance level of 0.05 is applied; thus, when the p-value is ≤ 0.05 , the null hypothesis is considered invalid and rejected, indicating a statistically significant result. Based on the table, H_1 ($UB \rightarrow IR$) and H_5 ($IB \rightarrow IR$) are not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$), while the other hypotheses are significant ($p \leq 0.05$).

Hypothesis Summary Tabel

Hypothesis	Path	t-value	P values	results
H1	UB • IR	0.126	0.900	Rejected
H2	VB • IR	3.249	0.001	Accepted
H3	RB • IR	3.028	0.002	Accepted
H4	TB • IR	2.320	0.020	Accepted
H5	IB • IR	0.137	0.891	Rejected
H6	TA • IR	2.863	0.004	Accepted
H7	IR • AU	9.410	0.000	Accepted

The result indicated that H_1 which hypothesized that Usage Barriers (UB) have a positive effect on Innovation Resistance (IR) in using OneFlux technology, is rejected. Although some users may experience usage barriers when operating the OneFlux system, most respondents appear to be already accustomed to using it in their daily tasks. As a result, these technical obstacles may be overshadowed by other types of barriers. This conclusion aligns with previous studies conducted by (Jiunn-Woei Lian, 2014), Hairafida, Asra, dan Sinnun (2025: 237), Softina, Amin, dan Wahyudi (2022: 32), dan Purwanto, Sjarief, dan Anwar (2020: 516) [21] [14], [15], [16] all of which found that usage barriers do not directly influence innovation resistance. H_2 which proposed that Value barriers (VB) positively affect Innovation Resistance (IR), is accepted. This may suggest that the value proposition of OneFlux has not been effectively communicated or socialized to employees. Many employees may not yet fully grasp the long-term vision or concrete benefits of the system. Similar conclusions were drawn in a study by Purwanto, Sjarief, dan Anwar (2020: 516)[16] which confirmed that value barriers directly impact innovation resistance. H_3 which stated that Risk barriers (RB) positively influence Innovation Resistance (IR), it also accepted. Users of OneFlux tend to resist changes when they perceive significant risks involved or when the promised benefits do not seem substantial enough to outweigh those risks. This finding is in line with the original work of (Ram, S. and Sheth, J.N., 1989)[22]. H_4 which suggested that Traditional Barriers (TB) positively affect Innovation Resistance (IR), is accepted. This result is consistent with findings by Softina, Amin, dan Wahyudi (2022: 33) [15], dan Purwanto, Sjarief, dan Anwar (2020: 516) [16] who confirmed that traditional work habits can significantly hinder the acceptance of new innovations. H_5 which hypothesized that Image barriers (IB) have a positive effect on Innovation Resistance (IR), is rejected. The insignificant effect of image barriers suggests that while users may hold some negative perceptions or stereotypes about the OneFlux system, these do not play a crucial role in their resistance. This might be because OneFlux is an internal corporate application, where external image or branding factors are less relevant compared to other functional or psychological concerns. This result is supported (SPIETH, SVEN HEIDENREICH and PATRICK, 2013)[23] who argued that image-related resistance tends to diminish over time as users gain more experience with an innovation, particularly when such barriers are perceptual rather than functional. H_6 which stated that Technology anxiety (TA) positively influences Innovation Resistance (IR) is accepted. This finding is consistent with research by Cao et al., (2020: 16) [17] which demonstrated that anxiety toward technology can intensify users' resistance to change. H_7 which proposed that Innovation Resistance (IR) has negative effect on Actual Usage (AU) of OneFlux technology, is accepted. This finding

supports the foundational premise of the Innovation Resistance Theory (IRT), as introduced by (Ram, S. and Sheth, J.N., 1989), which posits that unmanaged resistance to innovation can hinder system usage. This reinforces the importance of proactively managing user resistance as part of a comprehensive strategy for implementing digital systems like OneFlux to ensure optimal adoption and utilization.

6. CONCLUSION

The analytical results lead to following conclusions:

6.1 Managerial implication

PT Dayamitra Telekomunikasi (Mitratel) is advised to focus on several key strategies to address innovation resistance toward the OneFlux CRM system. The company should prioritize enhancing the perceived value of OneFlux so that employees clearly understand its practical benefits. Additionally, it is essential to mitigate perceived risk barriers by ensuring the system's reliability and providing strong user support. Efforts should also be made to reduce traditional barriers by encouraging changes in work habits and emphasizing the inefficiencies of outdated methods. Furthermore, addressing technology anxiety through continuous training and support is crucial. These efforts are essential to reduce resistance and ensure successful implementation of the OneFlux system across all organizational units, ultimately supporting the company's digital transformation goals.

6.2 Theoretical implication

Most prior studies using the Innovation Resistance Theory (IRT) have focused on consumer behavior and technologies adopted voluntarily, such as financial services or health apps. This study, however, applies and tests the IRT model in a mandatory system usage context, which is rarely explored—specifically, the OneFlux system in an organizational environment. This research expands the IRT framework by introducing Technology Anxiety as an additional predictor of Innovation Resistance. This extension enriches the theoretical literature by highlighting the emotional and psychological dimensions involved in adopting technology that users are required to use. This contribution helps deepen the understanding of user resistance in enterprise digital systems and opens pathways for further research in similar contexts.

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